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Research Article

**CLINICAL ANALYSIS OF COMPLETE DENTURE
SATISFACTION FACTORS: PATIENT AND DENTIST
VIEWPOINT**Dr. Umar Iqbal¹, Dr. Arbaz Ali Shah², Dr. Ahmed Bilal³¹Punjab Dental Hospital Lahore²de'Montmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore³Lahore Medical and Dental College, Lahore**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: The dilemma of patient satisfaction vs. non-satisfaction with dentures is another never-ending debate in dentistry. The fabrication of optimal dentures is possible with appropriate prosthetic laboratory techniques along with patients' anatomic and physiologic requirements assessed by a dentist.

Purpose: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the patient's priority and average patient and dentist satisfaction scores during treatment with full dentures.

Place and Duration: The study was conducted at the Dental department of Punjab Dental Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from May 2019 to April 2020.

Material and methods: After selecting the subjects based on the established inclusion and exclusion criteria, the patients were asked to fill in the VAS form. Proforma contained a questionnaire divided into 3 parts that must be completed independently by the patient and the doctor. Patients rated their dentures on a scale of 1-5 (5 = very satisfied; 4 = satisfied; 3 = neither dissatisfied nor dissatisfied; 2 = dissatisfied; 1 = very dissatisfied) and the dentist rated the quality of the denture and the denture bearing area.

Results: According to the patient's priority the majority of the patients preferred mastication (47%). The highest mean dentist satisfaction score was concerned with the extension of a denture (0.97 ± 0.28). There was no statistically significant difference with age and gender for mean denture assessment, aesthetic, phonetics, mastication and comfort satisfaction score ($p > 0.05$). However, the employed patients have aesthetic, phonetics and mastication satisfaction score higher than unemployed patients and the relationship was statistically significant (p less than 0.05). The educated patients have mean phonetics satisfaction score higher as compared to uneducated patients and the relationship was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Most of the patients noted the better chewing function with the dentures. Age and gender do not affect patient satisfaction. However, the employed patients were less satisfied with their prostheses compared to the unemployed. In addition, patients who were educated had better phonetics with prostheses compared to uneducated patients. Strong dentist-patient communication is essential to keep the patient happy.

Keywords: Complete denture, Satisfaction, Communication with the Patient.

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INTRODUCTION:

According to WHO research, the age group of people over 50 is growing worldwide. A number of agencies are also working to increase the life expectancy of the population in many countries. The 2014 UN surveys found that the age group of people over 65 is increasing day by day in Pakistan. From the dentist's point of view, tooth loss is fatal, in other words, it is the final death of a tooth or the end of a patient's oral disease¹⁻². All over the world, elderly patients are more likely to suffer from edentulous symptoms³⁻⁴. In Canada, 17% of the population had edentulousness in 1990, and now in the US it is 9.7% in the age group over 18. The study showed a dramatic increase in edentulousness, 33.1% of the population aged 65 or over suffered from the disease. A 2014 Lahore study of 279 women found that 231 (82.8%) of the subjects were completely edentulous in both arches, and the rest of the patients had missing teeth in one arch⁵⁻⁶. Despite various advances in dentistry and in the age of dental implants, full dentures are important in geriatric dentistry. The dilemma of patient satisfaction versus dissatisfaction with dentures is another endless debate in dentistry. The production of optimal dentures is possible with the use of appropriate prosthetic laboratory techniques, taking into account the anatomical and physiological requirements of the patient, assessed by the dentist⁷⁻⁸. A study evaluating patients' opinions about the satisfaction with their prostheses showed that a large proportion of patients are fully satisfied with the average prosthesis, while despite the correct performance of the prosthesis according to prosthetic criteria, many patients are still not satisfied with the function of the prosthesis. A literature review suggests that successful rehabilitation with a complete prosthesis depends not only on dentist and laboratory modulated factors but also on patient dependent factors. The consistency of saliva, the anatomical stability of the alveolar process and the underlying soft tissues, the depth of the fissures and the limitations of the neutral zone are important factors affecting the stability of the prosthesis. Ultimately, it negatively affects patient satisfaction⁹. In a survey conducted by Bhat VS9 in India, clinical factors influencing patient satisfaction with full dentures were assessed. This survey evaluates the patient as being very happy, happy, and average level of satisfaction. It was found that 21% of patients were very satisfied with the retention of the upper prosthesis and 23% very satisfied with the maintenance of the lower prosthesis. Similarly, Fenlon MR also found that retention and stability are dependent on the condition of the mandibular alveolar process, and that its reproducibility should therefore be a major determinant of the patient's adaptability and satisfaction with new dentures.

Facial aesthetics and phonetics are also considered the main determinants of satisfaction considered in the present study as well as in previous literature. The same Indian study found that 53% were very satisfied with the physical change of the face and only 13% were dissatisfied. However, 25% were very satisfied with the speech adaptation, while 35% were unable to achieve optimal phonetics with the prosthesis. Another factor that is considered to be the primary condition for patient satisfaction is adequate chewing needs. About 22% were satisfied with their chewing needs and 3% were not satisfied with chewing with the new full dentures. As mentioned earlier, various psychosocial, psychological and socio-cultural factors are also taken into account when assessing the effectiveness of treatment with full dentures. Ali, HI, also found in the study that the level of literacy, individual perception, mental state, and socioeconomic status of the patient also negatively or positively influenced the patient's satisfaction with the prosthesis. A study conducted in India looked at the prevalence of tooth lessness among women with different socio-economic status and the need for prosthetic rehabilitation. It found that 59.1% of the population with low socioeconomic status was prone to tooth loss and required full and partial dentures. In addition, in such cases, long-term tooth loss and poor oral hygiene are factors responsible for anatomical changes in the oral cavity and ultimately dissatisfaction with prosthetic rehabilitation. It is important for the doctor to take into account that the patient is the one who has already suffered from the disease and any complications and dissatisfaction that increase his troubles. The ultimate goal of any treatment is to provide maximum benefit to the patient¹⁰. Therefore, studies have been carried out to improve the quality of a complete prosthesis by examining the patient's opinion. The aim of this study is to assess the satisfactory parameters for both the patient and the dentist, and to assess the patient's priority when making the prosthesis. Therefore, the aim of the research was to improve the quality of the patient's health care, and ultimately the quality of life after dental restoration.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted at the Dental department of Punjab Dental Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from May 2019 to April 2020. The sample size was estimated using the WHO sample size calculator, assuming patient satisfaction statistics at the level of 3.98 ± 1.12 , margin of error at 0.205 and 95%. The calculated sample size was 115. Patients were recruited by sampling without probability after obtaining consent from an ethical point of view. The study included edentulous patients who required full dentures, aged 48-65 years, of both sexes, without any systemic diseases.

The study excluded patients who were mentally retarded and did not consent. The data was collected using a verified Cronbach's α -questionnaire of 85%. Proforma has been divided into sociodemographic, patient priority, dentist satisfaction through denture evaluation, and patient satisfaction. This proforma was to be filled in independently by both the patient and the dentist. Patients and dentist rated their satisfaction with dentures on a Likert scale of 1-5 (5 = very satisfied; 4 = satisfied; 3 = neither dissatisfied nor dissatisfied; 2 = dissatisfied; 1 = very dissatisfied). SPSS version 23 was used to analyze the data. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for quantitative variables such as age, while frequencies and percentages were calculated for

qualitative variables such as gender, employment status, and education. A descriptive analysis of dentist and patient satisfaction was also performed. An independent t-test was used to compare the assessment of prosthesis, aesthetics, phonetics, chewing parameters and comfort with age, gender, and employment and educational status. $P \leq 0.05$ was assumed as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 115 participants took part in the study. The mean age of the patients was 58.28 ± 7.02 years. Most of the patients were male (52.2%) and 47.8% were female. Most of them were unemployed (73%) and had a primary school (74.8%) (Table 1).

Table 1 Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Quantitative Variables	Mean	SD
Age (Years)	58.28	7.02
Qualitative Variables	n	%
Gender		
Male	60	52.2%
Female	55	47.8%
Employment Status		
Unemployed	84	73.0%
Employed	22	19.1%
Self-employed	9	7.8%
Educational status		
Uneducated	6	5.2%
Primary schooling	86	74.8%
Postgraduate	23	20.0%

Depending on the patient's priority, most patients preferred chewing (47%), followed by aesthetics (28.7%), phonetics (13.9%) and comfort (10.4%). The highest mean dentist satisfaction score was for denture extension (0.97 ± 0.28), and the lowest for occlusion (0.79 ± 0.41). The average result of satisfaction with the appearance of the face with prostheses is high in terms of aesthetic parameters and amounts to 4.50 ± 1.09 . The average satisfaction score from the feeling of confidence

during the conversation with the prosthesis was assessed as high in the phonetic parameters (4.32 ± 1.05). The average result of satisfaction with prostheses helpful in eating food is defined as high in the chewing parameters (4.30 ± 1.35). The average satisfaction score for the absence of painful areas caused by the prosthesis is assessed as high in the comfort parameters (4.91 ± 0.41) (Table 2).

Table 2 Descriptive analysis of satisfaction of dentist and patients

Part A		
Denture Assessment	Mean	SD
Quality of Fit (Retention)	0.93	0.26
Extension	0.97	0.18
Vertical Relation	0.91	0.28
Occlusion	0.79	0.41
Part B		
Aesthetic		
Have missing teeth made an impact on your profile?	0.76	0.43
Do you avoid laughing or smiling with missing teeth?	0.23	0.43
Do you avoid conversation with others due to missing teeth?	0.24	0.43
Are you afraid to visit an occasion without your teeth?	0.39	0.49
Are you satisfied with your facial appearance with dentures?	4.50	1.09
Are you satisfied with the size, shape, and color of the teeth?	4.46	1.12
Phonetics		
Do you have a speech problem due to missing teeth?	0.56	0.5
Does air blow out during speech?	0.41	0.49
Do you often avoid people due to a speech problem?	0.26	0.44
Has a speech problem affected your profession?	0.45	0.5
Are you satisfied with your speech with dentures?	4.13	1.1
Do you feel confident when you speak with a denture?	4.34	1.05
Mastication		
Has your chewing capability been compromised without teeth?	0.97	0.18
Has your ability to engulf food been affected?	0.74	0.44
Has your diet selection changed?	0.62	0.49
Do you avoid eating with others?	0.20	0.40
Has a loss of teeth affected your digestion and general health?	0.43	0.50
Are your dentures helpful in eating food?	4.30	1.35
Do your upper denture falling down while opening the mouth?	0.19	0.40
Does your lower denture get displaced on tongue movements?	0.46	0.50
Comfort		
Do you have pain while opening or closing the mouth with dentures?	0.08	0.27
Do you have even contact of teeth on both sides while closing the mouth?	0.78	0.41
Have you had sore spots due to dentures?	4.91	0.41
Have felt that your denture has not been fitting properly?	0.39	0.49

The dentist and patient satisfaction score were stratified by age, gender, employment status, and education. There was no statistically significant difference between the age group (0.05) in terms of the mean prosthesis, aesthetics, phonetics, chewing and comfort satisfaction. Likewise, no statistical significance was observed between males and females ($p > 0.05$) for the mean prosthesis, aesthetics, phonetics, chewing and comfort satisfaction ratings. The employed patients have a higher satisfaction with aesthetics, phonetics and chewing scores than the unemployed, and this relationship was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3 Comparison of dentist and patient's satisfaction score with age and gender

Age Groups	<60 years (n=77)		≥ 60 years (n=38)		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Denture assessment	3.64	0.74	3.53	0.76	0.46
Aesthetic	10.32	2.19	11.11	2.29	0.08
Phonetics	10.19	2.5	10.05	2.32	0.77
Mastication	8.06	1.95	7.61	2.25	0.26
Comfort	6.12	6.26	0.78	0.69	0.33
Gender	Male (n=60)		Female (n=55)		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Denture assessment	3.57	0.77	3.64	0.73	0.620
Aesthetic	10.60	2.22	10.56	2.29	0.930
Phonetics	10.23	2.40	10.05	2.49	0.690
Mastication	7.95	2.09	7.87	2.04	0.840
Comfort	6.13	0.77	6.20	0.73	0.640
Employment Status	Employed (n=31)		Unemployed (n=84)		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Denture assessment	3.68	0.75	3.57	0.75	0.502
Aesthetic	9.68	2.55	10.92	2.04	0.008
Phonetics	9.35	2.46	10.44	2.38	0.033
Mastication	7.29	2.18	8.14	1.97	0.048
Comfort	6.16	0.93	6.17	0.67	0.973
Education status	Educated (n=98)		Uneducated (n=17)		P-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Denture assessment	3.59	0.77	3.65	0.61	0.780
Aesthetic	10.5	2.38	11.06	1.14	0.345
Phonetics	10.42	2.42	8.59	1.97	0.004
Mastication	7.86	2.15	8.24	1.39	0.486
Comfort	6.16	0.74	6.18	0.81	0.947

Educated patients have a higher average score of satisfaction with phonetics compared to uneducated people, and this relationship was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3).

DISCUSSION:

The study aims to assess the patient's priority in the manufacture of the prosthesis, as well as assess how satisfied patients were with receiving the prosthesis in terms of aesthetics, phonetics, chewing and comfort. The study also determined the satisfaction parameters of a successful prosthesis. Berg E found that a healthy, constructive, open and practical discussion between a dentist and his patient reflects the successful performance of a denture¹¹. Ever since toothlessness has become a legendary tradition in old age, there is always a need for prosthetic rehabilitation. It is extremely important for the dentist to consider the patient's priorities in making

dentures. Toothlessness and old age add up to increase the level of irritability in the patient's behavior¹². According to the current research results, 47% of patients prefer to include features in the prosthesis that could improve their chewing ability. This explains that a prosthesis is one way to improve the overall quality of life as toothlessness has a negative impact on the patient's well-being. The second parameter in this aspect is aesthetics. It shows that 28.7% of the patients chose an aesthetic denture rather than the right mastic and comfort. This suggests that social embarrassment may play an important role in toothless patients. The other two parameters, phonetics and comfort, were the least noticeable¹³. Only 13.9% of patients required

appropriate phonetics with prostheses. Indeed, speech is one of the major contributors to edentulousness, but the results are obvious and luckily it is the least reported problem for most patients. Taking into account the socio-demographic status of the patients, the mean age of the patients was 58.28 ± 7.02 years, of which 52.2% were male and 47.8% female. About 73% of patients were unemployed (73%), while 27% were employed. The sociodemographic importance in assessing patient satisfaction is one of the main strengths. Determines whether the patient's satisfaction is affected by age, gender or employment status. Satisfaction is a variable parameter and is subjective to the patient's demographics, but it is worth noting that regardless of the patient's age and gender, satisfaction never changes. Hence, age and sex do not seem to be a risk factor for satisfaction, which is also confirmed in the conducted studies¹⁴. In line with the patient's priorities, employment is one of the parameters influencing his satisfaction. In this study, it is justified that the employed patients had an average aesthetic satisfaction score of 9.68 ± 2.55 , an average level of phonetic satisfaction of 9.35 ± 2.46 and an average level of satisfaction with chewing 7.29 ± 2.18 , i.e. less than unemployed. The result showed a statistically significant relationship between satisfaction with aesthetics, phonetics and chewing. When considering these results, it is worth noting that the employed patients were less satisfied with the aesthetics of post-prosthesis therapy, which may be due to social life. The level of satisfaction of the employed patients was higher because they had a greater influence of edentulousness on their profile (mean satisfaction score 0.76 ± 0.43); they had to avoid laughing (average satisfaction score 0.23 ± 0.43), conversations (average satisfaction score 0.24 ± 0.43) with their colleagues, which also causes them a great social dilemma affecting their profession (average satisfaction score 0.45 ± 0.50). Moreover, they had difficulty speaking (mean satisfaction score 0.56 ± 0.50) and blowing air while speaking (mean satisfaction score 0.41 ± 0.49). The most important factor influencing chewing in these patients was the fear of the upper prosthesis falling out while opening the mouth (mean satisfaction score 0.19 ± 0.40), which is a social injury and has a negative impact on the patient's well-being. It is also worth noting that these patients do not prefer eating with anyone (average satisfaction score 0.20 ± 0.40). The results are consistent with the Santos BF study and many other studies. In this study, phonetics is one of the factors related to the educational status of the patient. Uneducated patients were not satisfied with speech with prostheses ($p < 0.05$). This shows that educated patients have learned phonetics and speech throughout their education compared to

uneducated patients. Therefore, educated patients were able to pronounce the alphabets correctly¹⁵. The results of this study concerning the comparison of satisfaction with dentures with age, gender, employment status and education were not statistically significant. However, the dentist had adequate prosthesis elongation (mean satisfaction score 0.97 ± 0.28), and the least satisfaction with occlusion (mean satisfaction score 0.79 ± 0.41). These results contradict the studies by Shirani et al. The study was limited to establishing average patient and dentist satisfaction scores. However, he does not assess whether better communication translates into greater satisfaction with the performance of the prosthesis.

CONCLUSION:

Successful prosthesis performance depends on patient satisfaction. In short, patients were generally satisfied with their dentures. Age and gender do not affect patient satisfaction. However, the employed patients were less satisfied with their prostheses compared to the unemployed. In addition, patients who were educated had better phonetics with prostheses compared to uneducated patients.

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